

Figure 25: the diagonal lines of the vāstu according to BS 52.61 and KI 54.20-22. The lines are laid over the elements of the 9x9 vāstu that the two texts have in common (see figures 5a and 5b and discussion at section 2.1.5 of the general introduction).



The nine points of intersection of the diagonals are termed atimarmans at the BS 52.62.